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Research Article

**STABILITY INDICATING METHOD DEVELOPMENT OF
RIMONABANT AND IT'S VALIDATION BY RP-HPLC AND
HPTLC METHOD****Bollepaka Srilatha¹, Santhosh Illendula².**

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Abstract:

A new simple, accurate, rapid, precise, reproducible and cost effective HPLC and HPTLC method for the quantitative estimation of Rimonabant in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage form. In Method using HPTLC, chromatograms were developed in a mobile phase of 2 mM Sodium dihydrogen orthophosphate (NaH₂PO₄)-Acetonitrile (38:62) for approximately 25 mins and detected at λ_{max} of 303 nm. Accuracy was found to be in the range of 98.31-102.25 % whereas intraday precision was found to be in the range of 0.03 to 1.60%. Interday precision was found to be 1.36, 0.74 and 0.31 at LQC, MQC and HQC, respectively. Response was found to be linear from concentration range 20-100 μ g/ml which was not an improvement over method of estimation by UV spectroscopy. To make more sensitive and suitable for analysis of low concentration samples a method using HPLC with UV detector was developed and validated.

In HPLC with UV detector, 20 μ l samples were loaded on a Lichrospher, C-18 (250 \times 4.6 mm, 5 μ m Merck, Germany) and were eluted in a mobile phase of 2 mM Sodium dihydrogen orthophosphate (NaH₂PO₄)-Acetonitrile (38:62) using an isocratic method at a flow rate of 1 ml/min. Whole eluate was detected at 303 nm. Quality control concentration selected were 2.5, 9 and 10 μ g/ml as low, mid and high QC. Accuracy was found to be in the range of 98.03-103.68 % whereas intraday precision was found to be in the range of 0.03 to 1.89%. Inter-day precision was found to be 1.52, 1.04 and 1.18 at LQC, MQC and HQC, respectively. It was found to be specific and linear from 2-20 μ g/ml.

In nut shell, all three methods developed and validated were accurate and precise. UV method being less cumbersome has its advantage over HPTLC whereas HPTLC method included separation of unwanted ingredients from analyte. HPLC method was more sensitive than other two methods and found suitable to analyze low concentration samples.

Keywords: Rimonabant, HPLC, HPTLC, Method development, Validation, ICH guidelines, Sodium dihydrogen orthophosphate, Accuracy, Precision.

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INTRODUCTION:

Rimonabant (rimonabant) was the first in a new class of therapeutic agents called Cannabinoid-1 Receptor Blockers (CB1). Rimonabant was studied for use in the treatment of obesity and related conditions. Rimonabant acts by selectively blocking CB1 receptors found in the brain and in peripheral organs important in glucose and lipid (or fat) metabolism, including adipose tissue, the liver, gastrointestinal tract and muscle. Rimonabant switches off the same brain circuits that make people hungry when they smoke cannabis.

CB1 receptor blockade with Rimonabant acts to decrease the overactivity of the endocannabinoid system (EC system).^{3,4} The EC system is a recently characterised physiological system that includes receptors such as the CB1 receptor and it has been shown to play an important role in regulating body weight and in controlling energy balance, as well as glucose and lipid (or fat) metabolism. Rimonabant was studied to be used complementary to diet and exercise to treat obese or overweight patients who suffer from type 2 diabetes and abnormal levels of fat in the blood. Sanofi argued that Rimonabant could also prevent the risk of cardiovascular disease. Patients with large waist circumference (102 cm in men and 88 cm in women) were said to most benefit from taking the drug.

Fig-1 Structure of Rimonabant Stability

During the earlier validation studies, the method developer gained some information on the stability of reagents, mobile phases, standards, and sample solutions. For routine testing in which many samples are prepared and analyzed each day, it is often essential that solutions be stable enough to allow for delays such as instrument breakdowns or overnight analyses using autosamplers. At this point, the limits of stability should be tested. Samples and standards should be tested over at least a 48-h period, and quantitation of components should be determined by comparison to freshly prepared standards. If the solutions are not stable over 48 h, storage conditions or additives should be identified that can improve stability. (Szostek *et al.*, 2006; Chandran and Singh, 2007)

An example of stability criteria for assay methods is that sample and standard solutions and the mobile

phase will be stable for 48 h under defined storage conditions. Acceptable stability is „ 2% change in standard or sample response, relative to freshly prepared standards. The mobile phase is considered to have acceptable stability if aged mobile phase produces equivalent chromatography (capacity factors, resolution, or tailing factor) and assay results are within 2% of the value obtained with fresh mobile phase. (Wang *et al.*, 2006; Abdelmageed, 2007)

For impurity methods, the sample and standard solutions and mobile phase will be stable for 48 h under defined storage conditions. Acceptable stability is „ 20% change in standard or sample response at the limit of quantitation, relative to freshly prepared standards. The mobile phase is considered to have acceptable stability if aged mobile phase produces equivalent chromatography and if impurity results at the limit of quantitation are within 20% of the values obtained with fresh mobile phase. (Green, 1996; Rogatsky *et al.*, 2006)

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Chemicals and Reagents: Acetonitrile (ACN), methanol (MeOH) were procured from Ranbaxy laboratories, SAS Nagar, India. Analytical grade Sodium dihydrogen orthophosphate, orthophosphoric acid, were procured from Qualigens Fine Chemicals, Mumbai, India. Glacial acetic acid and ammonium acetate GR

Instruments:

HPTLC system (CAMAG, Switzerland), HPLC system (SHIMADZU, Kyoto, Japan), Electronic Balance (CITIZEN BALANCE BL-220H), Ultra Sonicator (ANALYTICAL), and P^H Analyzer (ELICO), Distillation unit (BOROSIL), Vacuum filtration unit (BOROSIL).

Method Development and Validation by HPTLC**Instrumentation and chromatographic conditions**

The HPTLC system (CAMAG, Switzerland) consisting of an automated multiple development (AMD 2) with automated TLC sampler (ATS III) and TLC scanner III conjugated with computer (Compaq, India) was used. A 20×20 cm RP-18, F_{254S} TLC plate was procured from Merck, India. Software platform to analyze chromatograms was winCATS version 1.4.2.8121. An aliquot of 25 µl of sample was sprayed on TLC plate using ATS III. Chromatograms were developed in a mobile phase of 2 mM Sodium dihydrogen orthophosphate (NaH₂PO₄)-Acetonitrile (38:62) for approximately 25 mins. Rimonabant was detected at λ_{max} of 303 nm. A 20×20 cm twin trough chromatographic chamber was used for development of chromatogram. It was saturated for 10 minutes

before use. A representative chromatogram has been shown in fig 1.1.

1.1.1 Stock and standard solutions

Figure 1.1: HPTLC -3D chromatogram

Accurately weighed 24.92 mg of Rimonabant was weighed and dissolved in methanol to give 1 mg/ml primary stock (PS) solution.

1.1.2 Preparation of calibration standards and quality control (QC) samples

Five point calibration curve was prepared in methanol using PS. Calibration standards (CS) were prepared using primary stock as given in Table 1.

Table 1: Preparation of Calibration Standards

Calibration Standards	Concentration (µg/ml)	Stock Volume (ml)	Vol. of Methanol (ml)	Final Volume (ml)
CS1	20	0.20	9.80	10
CS2	40	0.40	9.60	10
CS3	60	0.60	9.40	10
CS4	80	0.80	9.20	10
CS5	100	1.00	9.00	10

Primary stock and calibration standards were prepared afresh daily. Primary stock of Rimonabant was unstable and therefore prepared freshly before every analysis. CS1 and CS5 were prepared in duplicate and one out of these samples was considered for calculation. Quality control (QC) samples were prepared in triplicate at three concentration levels viz. 30 µg/ml (QC low), 50 µg/ml (QC mid) and 90 µg/ml (QC high). QC samples were prepared from WS by suitable dilution in methanol given in Table 2.

Table 2: Preparation of Quality Control (QC) Samples

Quality Control Standards	Concentration (µg/ml)	Stock Volume (ml)	Vol. of Methanol (ml)	Final Volume (ml)
LQC	30	0.30	9.70	10
MQC	50	0.50	9.50	10
HQC	90	0.90	9.10	10

1.2 Method Validation

1.2.1 HPTLC system reproducibility The HPLC system reproducibility was checked with five replicate injections of each analytical standard ranging from 20 µg/ml to 100 µg/ml.

1.3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

1.3.1 System Reproducibility

System reproducibility was checked everyday using repeat injection in the range of 20-100 µg/ml and CV % was found to be less than ±1 %.

1.3.2 Accuracy and Precision

Intraday and Inter-day accuracy precision was determined using three replicates at each QC levels on three different days. Accuracy was found to be in the range of 98.31-102.25 % whereas intraday precision was found to be in the range of 0.03 to 1.60%. Inter-day precision was found to be 1.36, 0.74 and 0.31 at LQC, MQC and HQC, respectively. Results have been shown in Table 3 and 4.

Table 3: Intraday accuracy precision on three different days

Intraday Precision-Accuracy						
Day	LQC	% ACC	MQC	% ACC	HQC	% ACC
Day 1						
Actual Conc.	30.27		49.84		88.64	
	29.76	98.31	49.61	99.53	88.67	100.03
	30.39	100.40	49.82	99.97	88.61	99.97
	30.67	101.32	50.11	100.54	88.64	100.01
Mean	30.27	100.01	49.85	100.01	88.64	100.00
SD	0.47	1.54	0.25	0.51	0.03	0.03
CV%	1.54	1.54	0.51	0.51	0.03	0.03
Day 2						
Actual Conc.	29.15		49.15		91.33	
	29.17	100.05	49.75	101.21	91.55	100.24
	29.58	101.49	49.47	100.66	91.19	99.85
	29.81	102.25	49.32	100.34	91.27	99.94
Mean	29.52	101.26	49.51	100.74	91.34	100.01
SD	0.33	1.12	0.22	0.44	0.19	0.20
CV%	1.10	1.10	0.44	0.44	0.20	0.20
Day 3						
Actual Conc.	30.66		49.55		91.83	
	30.20	98.52	50.17	101.25	91.93	100.11
	30.93	100.89	49.12	99.12	91.78	99.94
	31.15	101.58	49.37	99.63	91.81	99.98
Mean	30.76	100.33	49.55	100.00	91.84	100.01
SD	0.49	1.61	0.55	1.11	0.08	0.09
CV%	1.60	1.60	1.11	1.11	0.09	0.09

Table 4: Interday precision and accuracy of different days

Interday Precision-Accuracy						
Day	LQC	P*	MQC	P*	HQC	P*
Day 1	29.76	0.98	49.61	1.00	88.67	1.00
	30.39	1.00	49.82	1.00	88.61	1.00
	30.67	1.01	50.11	1.01	88.64	1.00
Day 2	29.17	1.00	49.75	1.00	91.55	1.00
	29.58	1.01	49.47	0.99	91.19	1.00
	29.81	1.02	49.32	0.99	91.27	1.00
Day 3	30.20	0.99	50.17	1.01	91.93	1.01
	30.93	1.01	49.12	0.99	91.78	1.01
	31.15	1.02	49.37	1.00	91.81	1.01
Mean	30.18	1.01	49.64	1.00	90.61	1.00
SD	--	0.01	--	0.01	--	0.00
CV%	--	1.36	--	0.74	--	0.31

*Concentration ratio (P) =Predicted Concentration/Actual Concentration

1.3.4 Linearity and Range

Response was found to be linear from concentration range 20-100 µg/ml. Regression coefficient, intercept and slope has been presented in Table 5.

Table 1.5: Slope, intercept and coefficient of correlation

Day	Slope	Intercept	R ²	R
Day1	77.06	529.49	0.9993	0.9996
Day2	104.17	117.57	0.9995	0.9997
Day3	106.61	79.04	0.9994	0.9997

Predicted concentration was divided by actual concentration to normalize and coefficients of variation at each concentration levels were calculated and presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Coefficient of variation at each concentration levels

Conc.(µg/ml)	Concentration ratio (P) at linearity points				
	20	40	60	80	100
Day 1	1.05	0.98	0.99	1.01	1.00
Day 2	1.00	1.02	0.98	1.00	1.00
Day 3	0.98	1.01	1.00	1.01	0.99
Mean	1.0089	1.0013	0.9880	1.0072	0.9992
SD	0.0373	0.0211	0.0081	0.0066	0.0067
CV	3.6939	2.1081	0.8227	0.6531	0.6692

1.4 CONCLUSION:

HPTLC method for estimation of Rimonabant in pharmaceutical formulations were developed and validated. Method was found to be capable of producing accurate and reproducible result within 20-100 µg/ml.

Method Development and Validation by HPLC-UV

Instrumentation and chromatographic conditions

The HPLC system (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan) consisting of a dual-piston reciprocating pump (LC-10 ATvp) with a system controller (SCL-10 Avp), a syringe loading injector (Model 7125i; rheodyne, cotati, CA, USA) and a UV-visible dual wavelength detector (SPD-10 AVvp) was used. Acquisitions and quantifications were done using CLASS-VP software. A 20 µl loop was used to load the samples on a Lichrospher, C-18 (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 µm Merck, Germany). Rimonabant samples were eluted in a

mobile phase of 2 mM Sodium dihydrogen orthophosphate (NaH₂PO₄)-Acetonitrile (38:62) using an isocratic method at a flow rate of 1 ml/min. Rimonabant was detected at λ_{max} of 303 nm. Column was equilibrated for approximately 30 min with initial condition before commencement of analysis and chromatography was carried out at ambient temperature.

2.1.1 Stock and standard solutions

Accurately weighed 24.92 mg of Rimonabant was weighed and dissolved in methanol to give 1 mg/ml primary stock solution. Working stock (WS) solution of 100 µg/ml was prepared by appropriate dilution in methanol.

2.1.2 Preparation of calibration standards and quality control (QC) samples

Eight point calibration curve was prepared in methanol using WS. Calibration standards (CS) were prepared using working stock as given in Table 7.

Table 7: Preparation of Calibration Standards

Calibration Standards	Concentration (µg/ml)	Stock Volume (ml)	Vol. of Methanol (ml)	Final Volume (ml)
CS1	2	0.20	9.80	10
CS2	5	0.50	9.50	10
CS3	8	0.80	9.20	10
CS4	10	1.00	9.00	10
CS5	12	0.60	4.40	5
CS6	15	0.75	4.25	5
CS7	18	0.90	4.10	5
CS8	20	1.00	4.00	5

Working stock and calibration standards were prepared afresh daily. Primary stock of Rimonabant was unstable and therefore prepared freshly before every analysis. CS1 and CS8 were prepared in duplicate and one out of these samples was considered for calculation. Quality control (QC) samples were prepared in triplicate at three concentration levels viz. 2.5 µg/ml (QC low), 9 µg/ml (QC mid) and 19 µg/ml (QC high). QC samples were prepared from WS by suitable dilution in methanol given in Table 8.

Table 8: Preparation of Quality Control (QC) Samples

Quality Control Standards	Concentration (µg/ml)	Stock Volume (ml)	Vol. of Methanol (ml)	Final Volume (ml)
CS1	2.5	0.25	9.75	10
CS2	9	0.90	9.10	10
CS3	19	0.95	4.05	5

2.2 Method Validation

2.2.1 HPLC system reproducibility

The HPLC system reproducibility was checked with five replicate injections of each analytical standard ranging from 2 µg/ml to 20 µg/ml.

2.3 Results and Discussion

2.3.1 System Reproducibility

System reproducibility was checked everyday using repeat injection in the range of 2-20 µg/ml and CV % was found to be less than ±1 %.

2.3.2 Accuracy and Precision

Intraday and Interday accuracy precision was determined using three replicates at each QC levels on three different days. Accuracy was found to be in the range of 98.03-103.68 % whereas intraday precision was found to be in the range of 0.03 to 1.89%. Interday precision was found to be 1.52, 1.04 and 1.18 at LQC, MQC and HQC, respectively. Results have been shown in Table 9 and 10.

Table 9: Intraday accuracy precision on three different days

Intraday Precision-Accuracy						
Day	LQC	% ACC	MQC	% ACC	HQC	% ACC
Day 1						
Actual Conc.	2.49	--	8.97	--	18.94	--
	2.49	99.95	8.79	98.03	19.37	102.29
	2.49	99.87	8.84	98.59	18.97	100.14
	2.48	99.61	8.98	100.10	19.14	101.06
Mean	2.49	99.81	8.87	98.91	19.16	101.16
SD	0.00	0.18	0.10	1.08	0.20	1.08
CV%	0.18	0.18	1.09	1.09	1.07	1.07
Day 2						
Actual Conc.	2.54	--	9.14	--	19.30	--
	2.63	103.68	9.10	99.49	19.51	101.08
	2.58	101.73	9.19	100.52	19.44	100.70
	2.59	101.87	9.25	101.21	19.38	100.42
Mean	2.60	102.43	9.18	100.41	19.45	100.73
SD	0.03	1.09	0.08	0.86	0.06	0.33
CV%	1.06	1.06	0.86	0.86	0.33	0.33
Day 3						
Actual Conc.	2.60	--	9.37	--	19.78	--
	2.61	100.24	9.26	98.81	20.12	101.70
	2.57	98.86	9.26	98.88	20.51	103.67

	2.59	99.47	9.26	98.84	19.74	99.82
Mean	2.59	99.52	9.26	98.84	20.12	101.73
SD	0.02	0.70	0.00	0.03	0.38	1.93
CV%	0.70	0.70	0.03	0.03	1.89	1.89

Table 10: Interday precision and accuracy of different days

Interday Precision-Accuracy						
Day	LQC	P*	MQC	P*	HQC	P*
Day 1	2.49	1.00	8.79	0.98	19.37	1.02
	2.49	1.00	8.84	0.99	18.97	1.00
	2.48	1.00	8.98	1.00	19.14	1.01
Day 2	2.63	1.04	9.10	0.99	19.51	1.01
	2.58	1.02	9.19	1.01	19.44	1.01
	2.59	1.02	9.25	1.01	19.38	1.00
Day 3	2.61	1.00	9.26	0.99	20.12	1.02
	2.57	0.99	9.26	0.99	20.51	1.04
	2.59	0.99	9.26	0.99	19.74	1.00
Mean	2.56	1.01	9.10	0.99	19.58	1.01
SD	--	0.02	--	0.01	--	0.01
CV%	--	1.52	--	1.04	--	1.18

*Concentration ratio (P) = Predicted Concentration/Actual Concentration

2.3.3 Limit of Detection and Limit of Quantitation

Limit of detection and Limit of quantitation was calculated using signal to noise ratio method. Signal ratio was obtained by serial dilution technique and at detectable and quantifiable concentration standard deviation was calculated. Limit of detection was found to be 100 ng/ml and limit of quantitation was found to be 1 µg/ml.

2.3.4 Linearity and Range

Response was found to be linear from concentration range 2-20 µg/ml. Regression coefficient, intercept and slope has been presented in Table 5.

Table 11: Slope, intercept and coefficient of correlation

Day	Slope	Intercept	R ²	R
Day1	37450.05	1129.25	0.9996	0.9998
Day2	40619.39	-1962.10	0.9997	0.9998
Day3	11622.15	1329.42	0.9995	0.9997

Predicted concentration was divided by actual concentration to normalize and coefficients of variation at each concentration levels were calculated and presented in Table 6.

Table 12: Coefficient of variation at each concentration levels

Conc.(µg/ml)	Concentration ratio (P) at linearity points							
	2	5	8	10	12	15	18	20
Day 1	1.00	1.00	1.01	0.98	1.01	1.00	1.01	0.99
Day 2	1.01	0.97	1.00	1.02	1.00	0.99	1.00	1.00
Day 3	1.01	0.99	0.99	0.98	1.02	1.01	1.00	0.99
Mean	1.01	0.99	1.00	0.99	1.01	1.00	1.00	1.00
SD	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00
CV	0.36	1.15	0.74	2.25	0.87	1.00	0.40	0.33

2.3.5 Specificity

Peak purity index was determined and it was found to be positive indicating thereby that there is single component eluting at the retention time of analyte. It has been represented in Fig 1. Ratio chromatogram also indicated that method was specific. Ratio chromatogram and chromatogram has been represented in fig 13, respectively.

Figure 11: HPLC chromatogram of Rimonabant

2.4 Conclusion

HPLC method for estimation of Rimonabant in pharmaceutical formulations were developed and validated (2 μ g-20 μ g/ml). Method was found to be sensitive, specific and capable of producing accurate and reproducible result.

SUMMARY:

In Method using HPTLC, chromatograms were developed in a mobile phase of 2 mM Sodium dihydrogen orthophosphate (NaH₂PO₄)-Acetonitrile (38:62) for approximately 25 mins and detected at λ_{max} of 303 nm. Accuracy was found to be in the range of 98.31-102.25 % whereas intraday precision was found to be in the range of 0.03 to 1.60%. Interday precision was found to be 1.36, 0.74 and 0.31 at LQC, MQC and HQC, respectively. Response was found to be linear from concentration range 20-100 μ g/ml which was not an improvement over method of estimation by UV spectroscopy. To make more sensitive and suitable for analysis of low concentration samples a method using HPLC with UV detector was developed and validated.

In HPLC with UV detector, 20 μ l samples were loaded on a Lichrospher, C-18 (250 \times 4.6 mm, 5 μ m Merck, Germany) and were eluted in a mobile phase of 2 mM Sodium dihydrogen orthophosphate (NaH₂PO₄)-Acetonitrile (38:62) using an isocratic method at a flow rate of 1 ml/min. Whole eluate was detected at 303 nm. Quality control concentration selected were 2.5, 9 and 10 μ g/ml as low, mid and

high QC. Accuracy was found to be in the range of 98.03-103.68 % whereas intraday precision was found to be in the range of 0.03 to 1.89%. Inter-day precision was found to be 1.52, 1.04 and 1.18 at LQC, MQC and HQC, respectively. It was found to be specific and linear from 2-20 μ g/ml.

In nut shell, all three methods developed and validated were accurate and precise. UV method being less cumbersome has its advantage over HPTLC whereas HPTLC method included separation of unwanted ingredients from analyte. HPLC method was more sensitive than other two methods and found suitable to analyze low concentration samples.

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